

Effect of stand establishment techniques on yield and economics of lowland irrigated rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Days to 50% flowering		Net income (Rs ha ⁻¹) ^a			Benefit-cost ratio		
	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean
T ₁ Transplanting	6.0	5.2	5.6	9.6	7.5	8.6	85.6	78.6	18,666	12,984	15,825	2.10	1.76	1.93
T ₂ Seedling throwing	4.9	4.7	4.8	8.1	6.9	7.5	85.2	79.0	14,853	12,605	13,732	2.01	1.86	1.93
T ₃ Wet seeding: broadcasting manually	6.1	5.3	5.7	9.3	7.6	8.4	76.8	73.0	21,551	16,529	19,039	2.51	2.16	2.33 ^b
T ₄ Wet seeding: drum seeder	6.1	5.3	5.6	9.1	7.5	8.3	76.8	72.8	21,214	15,959	18,587	2.48	2.11	2.29 ^b
CD at 5%	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.53	0.55	0.11	2.0	1.7	na	na	na	na	na	na

^aUS\$1 = Rs 46. ^bAdditional seed cost also included. na = not applicable.

practices reduced the time to 50% flowering by 6 and 9 d in the wet and dry seasons, respectively, since the seedlings did not suffer from transplanting shock as in transplanting and seedling throwing. Santhi et al (1998) reported similar benefits of direct seeding over transplanting.

Thus, direct (wet) seeding, preferably through the drum seeder, could be recommended wherever labor is scarce and costly. In this way, farmers could obtain higher net incomes besides shortening the field-use duration in lowland irrigated rice.

References

- Matsushima S. 1980. Rice cultivation for millions. Tokyo (Japan): Japan Scientific Societies Press. p 239–242.
- Santhi P, Ponnusamy K, Kembuchetty N. 1998. A labor-saving technique in direct sown and transplanted rice. *Int Rice Res. Notes* 23(2):35–36.

Influence of seedling age and number of seedlings on yield attributes and yield of hybrid rice in the wet season

M.A.H. Molla, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya (BCKV), Department of Agronomy, Mohanpur 741252, West Bengal, India E-mail: drzaman@cal3.vsnl.net.in

In the irrigated rice ecosystem that uses high-yielding varieties (HYVs), yields have already started plateauing. In India, where it is not possible to put more area into rice cultivation, adopting hybrids with suitable management practices would certainly be an alternative for increasing rice productivity. A study conducted at the C Block Seed Farm of BCKV during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons examined the performance of hybrids as well as HYVs with different seedling ages and seedling number hill⁻¹.

The field was sandy loam to clay loam with a neutral soil reaction. Seeds were collected from the Rice Research Station in

Chinsurah. Treatments consisted of two hybrid rice cultivars (Pro-Agro 6201 and CNRH 3) and one HYV (IET4786), two seedling ages (21 and 28 d), and two levels of seedling number hill⁻¹ (1 and 2 seedlings hill⁻¹ for hybrid rice and 3 and 6 seedlings hill⁻¹ for the HYV). The crop was transplanted in the last week of July for both seasons using the rectangular planting method. The spacing was 20 cm × 10 cm. A dose of 80 kg N, 17.6 kg P, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied under recommended practices of split doses of N and K. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Results revealed that Pro-Agro 6201 gave a significantly higher yield

than IET4786, not only because of more mature panicles m⁻² but also because of a higher number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ and greater seed weight. Pro-Agro 6201 showed a more profuse tillering habit at an early stage than the HYV, which could be due to hybrid vigor (heterosis). Twenty-eight-day-old seedlings produced more tillers, panicles m⁻², and grain yield than did 21-d-old seedlings, which performed poorly because of insufficient growth at earlier stages. Seedlings hill⁻¹ significantly influenced number of tillers and mature panicles m⁻² and, consequently, rice yield. Two seedlings hill⁻¹ gave a significantly higher yield than one seedling, along with

Effect of seedling age and seedling number hill⁻¹ on yield and yield attributes of hybrid rice.

Treatment	Tillers m ⁻² (no.)		Mature panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1998	1999	1998	1999	1998	1999	1998	1999	1998	1999
<i>Cultivar</i>										
Pro-Agro 6201	422	419	332	335	83.2	86.0	21.74	21.64	5.6	5.5
CNRH 3	410	409	319	317	80.0	81.0	21.38	21.41	5.3	5.3
IET4786	345	349	266	268	75.4	76.7	21.16	21.33	4.2	4.1
CD (5%)	9.6	8.7	7.0	6.3	2.38	2.30	0.124	0.112	0.178	0.172
<i>Age of seedling</i>										
21 d old	388	385	300	301	78.8	80.6	21.42	21.40	4.8	4.8
28 d old	402	400	311	312	80.2	82.1	21.44	21.42	5.3	5.1
CD (5%)	7.9	7.1	5.7	5.1	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.145	0.139
<i>Seedling number hill⁻¹</i>										
<i>Hybrid</i>										
1	406	408	318	320	83.3	84.0	21.60	21.50	5.3	5.3
2	424	422	333	332	79.9	83.4	21.52	21.55	5.6	5.5
<i>HYV</i>										
3	345	342	261	265	77.0	75.9	21.02	21.35	4.1	4.1
6	363	356	270	272	73.8	77.5	21.30	21.31	4.4	4.1
CD (5%)	18.5	12.3	10.0	8.9	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.251	0.221

^aCD = coefficient of determination.

other parameters in hybrid cultivars. For the HYV, no significant response was obtained by increasing the number of seedlings from

three to six (see table). Thus, it was concluded that hybrid Pro-Agro 6201 could be grown profitably, replacing IET4786 (HYV)

using 28-d-old seedlings transplanted at two seedlings hill⁻¹. Three seedlings hill⁻¹ were sufficient for growing IET4786.

Effect of cooking on aleurone in the caryopsis of indica rice

A.B. Nadaf and S. Krishnan, Department of Botany, Goa University, Goa 403206, India

Aleurone, the principal nourishing layer in the rice grain, consists of one to several layers of uniform, highly differentiated cells (Beteke et al 1997). In cooking, the starchy components in the caryopsis expand both laterally and vertically. This study was undertaken to determine the effect of cooking on aleurone in the rice caryopsis. Local varieties used in this study were long-, medium-, and short-grain types. Rice grains were dehusked manually and cooked in a domestic cooker with excess water, with and without aleurone. To attain a caryopsis without aleurone, the aleurone layer was manually removed. For the measurement, an average of 100 grains was used.

The caryopsis cooked with aleurone showed three specific patterns of aleurone breakage—breakage at one end, breakage at both ends, and longitudinal breakage. Longitudinal breakage was maximum in all varieties, except Ambemohar. Varieties Ghansal and Kothmirsal were followed by IET lines, Pusa Basmati, Kernal Local, Jaya, and Jyoti with one-end breakage. IET15392 and IET13549 recorded 100% longitudinal breakage of aleurone. Local short-grain varieties such as Ambemohar, Ghansal, and Kothmirsal showed maximum breakage at one end. The caryopsis cooked without aleurone showed maximum elongation in all varieties studied (see figure).

The caryopsis cooked with aleurone acted as a limiting factor to the expansion. However, the pressure exerted by the components made the aleurone layer break (see figure).

The table shows that the caryopsis cooked with aleurone, which broke at both ends, had the maximum length, whereas the grain with longitudinal breakage had maximum breadth. Among the varieties studied, IET15396 had the maximum length (2–13 cm), with breakage at two ends; maximum breadth was recorded in Jyoti (0.54 cm), with longitudinal breakage. Data show that longitudinal breakage is directly proportional to grain length.